

Arsenic adsorption on rusting iron nails

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Abstract : The objective of the study was to sequestrate inorganic arsenic from groundwater using 6 mm rusting iron nails as well as to know maximum adsorption capacity of arsenic per g nail, rate of adsorption (*k*) at different ages of nails by batch study and to know practical applicability of nails by column study at pH around 7.5. It is observed that rate of removal for As(III) is slightly better than As(V). Maximum adsorption capacity was found for anoxic As(III), anoxic As(V), oxic As(III) and oxic As(V) were found as 528.32, 488, 531.87 and 516.25 µg per g of nail respectively when the initial concentration was 500 µg/L. Break-through for anoxic As(III), anoxic As(V), oxic As(III) and oxic As(V) were found in 186, 163, 174 and 176 days respectively when the initial concentration of 500 µg/L was used for each case on a daily basis. W-Scanning Electron Microscope (W-SEM) and Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDS) results showed evidence of surface deposition of arsenic on iron nails. XPS results showed the formation of different oxides with arsenic on the iron surface. A 7 cm diameter and 11.5 cm long column having 1500 g rusting nails were used to know practical applicability of rusting nail iron nails to sequestrate arsenic from water. 380 lit. As(III), 240 lit. As(V) and 200 lit. 1 : 1 total arsenic of 100 µg/L was passed through the column at flow rate of 32–40 ml/min before outlet concentration coming above 10 µg/L.

Keywords : Arsenic adsorption, rusting iron nails, maximum adsorption capacity, rate of removal.

I. Introduction

Arsenic is a colorless, odorless, tasteless toxic and carcinogenic metalloid element. Arsenic exists in various oxidation state of +5 (arsenate), +3 (arsenite), 0 (elemental arsenic) and -3 (arsine). In aqueous environment, arsenic mainly exists in +5 (e.g. AsO_4^{3-}) and +3 (e.g. AsO_3^{3-})¹ and As(III) (arsenite) is almost 10 times more soluble and toxic than As(V) (arsenate)². Dissolved arsenic is sequestered well by metallic iron as well as iron oxides³⁻⁵. Strong affinity of arsenates found for iron oxide⁶. For low concentration of arsenic, amorphous iron hydroxide can be used to remove arsenic⁷. Granular ferric hydroxide is effective in removing both As(III) and As(V) at pH of 7.6⁸. The maximum As(III) adsorption capacity was 3.5 mg of As(III)/g of NZVI⁹. Sorption capacity of magnetite nanoparticles depends on the

adsorbent surface area and pH value of the system¹⁰. Oxides and hydroxides formed due to iron corrosion have large surface area facilitating sorption or coprecipitation¹¹. So, rusting iron nails which are cheap, easily available and consist both metallic iron as well as iron oxides could remove arsenic well from water.

II. Materials and methods

Chemicals which were used during the study were of analytical grade. All the glass wares were cleaned with 2% nitric acid, rinsed with de-ionized water from Milli-Q (Millipore, USA) and oven dried at 180°C.

A. Chemicals

All chemicals were of analytical grade from Loba Chemie (Mumbai), Merck (Germany) and Fluka

(UK). De-ionized water from Milli-Q (Millipore, USA) was used for preparing all standard solutions. Inorganic As(III) and As(V) stock solution (1000 mg/L) were of analytical grade from Fluka. As(III) standard solution of 1000 mg/L was prepared by dissolving 0.867 g of sodium arsenite (NaAsO_2) from Loba Chemie adjusting to a volume of 500 ml in a volumetric flask with de-ionized water from Milli-Q. Further dilution was made from 1000 mg/L of stock solution using de-ionized water to prepare standards of 10 mg/L, 1 mg/L, 500 ppb, 100 ppb etc. For quantification of As(V); I have used reducing agent to convert As(V) to As(III) followed by quantification of As(III). For the reducing agent, thiosulphate solution was prepared by dropwise adding 5 ml of 10% v/v supra pure H_2SO_4 to 10 ml sodium metabisulfite solution (14% w/v), followed by addition of 10 ml sodium thiosulfate solution (1.4% w/v) and 0.2 g L-ascorbic acid (VA Application Work AW IN4-0101-102005, Micro Devices Metrohm Limited). While making the reducing agent, it was ensured that the solution was continuously shaken for getting well mix condition as well as to ensure that SO_2 gas is expelled out completely from the solution. The 1 ml reducing agent was added to 10 ml of sample with proper mixing, sealed and left for reduction for 3 h.

B. Sampling and pre treatment

For this study, groundwater sample was collected from a tube well at Pradhan Gate of Nankari Area which is just outside of IIT Kanpur campus. Samples were preserved at 4°C in polyethylene bottles. Samples having water quality parameters like pH 7.4–7.6, arsenic – not detectable, DO < 1.5 mg/L, alkalinity 300–320 mg/L, hardness 170–200 mg/L, conductivity 2400–2420 $\mu\text{mho/cm}$, phosphate 0.02–0.04 mg/L, sulphate 120–130 mg/L, temperature 24°C.

C. Iron nails

Most nails are made of steel. Galvanized iron nails are coated with zinc to make them corrosion resistant. The nails which were used for the study bought from the local market of Kanpur, the length of 6 mm, vendor name Mayur Pvt. Ltd. Nails size of

less than 6 mm would have been better adsorbent for arsenic as it possesses more surface area. Rusting nails which were used for arsenic removal from water contained around 62.42% oxygen, 37.59% iron by mass (W-SEM result). The surface area of nails was 1.02 m^2/g , average pore size (radius) = $4.65507e + 01 \text{ \AA}$, total pore volume = $2.388e - 03 \text{ g/cc}$ for pores smaller than 1984.3 \AA (radius) which were determined by BET N_2 adsorption analysis or BET surface area analyzer (Model Autosorb I, Quatachrome Corp). For the study, the iron nails were the first acid washed by 2% nitric acid, soaked in de-ionized water for 30 min and then oven dried at 180°C for 24 h to remove galvanized coating. Those iron nails were used for experiments.

D. Experimental

D.1. Batch experiments for determination of rate of adsorption (*k*) of arsenic :

To determine the kinetics of the adsorption i.e. rate of arsenic adsorption (*k*) by iron nails for As(III) and As(V); batch experiments were done. The anoxic water sample was prepared by purging N_2 gas at 0.1 kg/cm^2 pressure for 1 h to ensure proper oxygen free sample. Then 5 g of rusting iron nails were added to different glass tubes of 40 ml volume. Anoxic As(III) and As(V) of 100 ppb concentration of 40 ml volume were added to each glass tubes. All glass tubes were sealed properly to maintain proper anoxic condition. At different present time period of 7, 15, 30, 60, 120, 240, 360 and 720 min; the water samples were collected from each glass tubes by separating those nails. The collected water samples then analyzed in voltammetry (VA Trace 797, Metrohm, Switzerland) for quantification of arsenic. The same procedure was followed to know the adsorption behavior of rusting nails at the different age of rust like 1 day, 13 days, 30 days, 45 days, 60 days etc.

D.2. Maximum adsorption capacity (*q*_{max}) of nails :

To know maximum adsorption capacity of arsenic per g of rusted nail; four different glass tubes of 40 ml volume were taken for analysis of four different cases like anoxic As(III), anoxic As(V), oxic As(III)

and oxic As(V). In each glass tube, 5 g of rusting iron nails were put and 40 ml of 500 ppb arsenic solution was added. Glass tubes were sealed and kept for 24 h at room temperature. After 24 h, only water samples were collected from glass tubes separating nails and poured into polypropylene co-polymer centrifuge tube. Separated water analyzed by voltammetry (VA Trace 797, Metrohm, Switzerland) to get the final concentration of anoxic As(III), anoxic As(V), oxic As(III) and oxic As(V). The same procedure was followed on daily basis to know the maximum adsorption capacity per g of nail assuming that adsorption on each nail was same.

D.3. Column test :

A plastic column of 11.5 cm long and 7 cm diameter was used to know the actual behavior of adsorption of arsenic on rusted nails in the practical field. A circular steel platform of 6.5 cm diameter was used inside the column to give proper support for 1500 g rusted iron nails to maintain a higher area at its mouth so as higher flow rate. Nominal depth of cotton is used over steel platform followed by 1 cm depth of 100 μ sized sand. 1500 g of rusted nails were placed over the sand layer when the filter was filled with water to maintain proper packing of nails inside the filter. The idea behind placing of cotton was to keep sand in its place. And the sand was used to remove turbidity and iron particles coming out from the above-rusted iron nails. Arsenic (As(III), As(V) and 1 : 1 total As) spiked in the tap water of 100 ppb concentration was passed through the column at a flow rate of 32–40 ml/min at 5 lit. and 20 lit per day basis. A water level height of 1 cm was maintained throughout the experiment so that all nails were totally submerged in water and every nail supposed to take part in the removal of arsenic from water. Samples were collected from the inlet to analyze arsenic (As(III), As(V) and 1 : 1 total As) in voltammetry to know the inflow concentration. Samples collected from outlet were analyzed in voltammetry for arsenic, in Microwave Plasma-Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (MPAES) for iron and in Nephelometer for turbidity. The experiment was continued until outflow arsenic concentration

exceeded 10 μ g/L which is the standard for arsenic in drinking water as per WHO and Bureau of Indian Standards (IS 3025 (Part 37)).

D.4. Tracer study :

A tracer study was carried out to know actual retention time and dispersion coefficient of filter for that flow rate (32–40 ml/min) which was maintained during the experiment. Nitrate (NO_3^-) tracer was used as there is no adsorption on iron (Öztürk and Bektaş, 2004). A nitrate stock solution of 1000 mg/L was prepared from AgNO_3 salt (M.W. 169.87). Further dilution was made by deionized water to prepare standard solution like 0, 25, 50, 75 and 100 mg/L. Each of those standards of 50 ml was passed through the saturated column and 50 ml outlet samples were collected from the bottom of the filter. Those samples were further analyzed in Nephelometer for turbidity to draw calibration curve. Deionized water continuously passed through the filter at a flow rate of 34 ml/L and maintained a water head of 1 cm. Nitrate standard of 100 mg/L of 100 ml was suddenly added to the filter for getting impulse load case. A continuous flow rate of 34 ml/min was also maintained after that. Water samples from outlet were collected at an interval of 2 min up to 18 min. The turbidity of those samples was measured and those turbidity values were used in calibration curve to get concentrations at different time interval.

To get the dispersion coefficient of arsenic inside the column, continuous loading of concentration 100 mg/L nitrate passed and outlet samples were collected at a time interval of 2 min starting from 0. The conductivity of each sample was measured to get concentration (from calibration curve) at different time interval.

III. Results and discussion

A. Characterization of ground water sample

The water sample collected from hand pump near Pradhan Gate, Nankari area, IIT Kanpur campus; was analyzed to get important water quality parameters like pH, alkalinity, hardness, DO, conductivity, the concentration of arsenic etc. The results are in Table 1.

Table 1. Water quality parameter of ground water sample

Water quality parameter	Value	Measured procedure/instrument	
pH	7.4–7.6	E _h -pH meter	
E _h (mV)	–90	E _h -pH meter	
Temperature (°C)	24	Thermometer	
Alkalinity (mg/L)	300–320	Titrating by HCl	
DO (mg/L)	Raw sample	1.33	
	After O ₂ purging	7.53	Azide modification of Winkler method
	After N ₂ purging	0.13	
Hardness (mg/L)	170–200	EDTA Titrimetric method	
Conductivity (µmho/cm)	2400–2420	Conductivity meter	
Sulphate (mg/L)	120–130	Turbidimetric method	
Total phosphates (mg/L)	0.02–0.03	Digestion technique	

B. Characterization of iron nails

B.1. Scanning Electron Microscopy (W-SEM)

result :

To know the surface morphology and approximate surface deposition of arsenic; iron nails were analyzed by Scanning Electron Microscopy (W-SEM) (Model JSM-6010 LA, JEOL, Japan). The SEM photomicrographs of deionized water washed raw rusted nails, nails with As(III) and nails with As(V) were done at 500 magnification which was shown Figs. 6, 7 and 8 respectively. Micrographs shown in figures clearly showing different surface texture and roughness. The change in surface texture and continuous oxide formation is possibly the reason behind the change of adsorption behavior over time. Energy Dispersive X-ray Microanalysis (EDXA/EDX) was performed to know the approximate quantity of arsenic deposited onto the surface of nails. Arsenic deposition is clearly visible on nails having anoxic As(III) and As(V); though the actual quantity of arsenic deposition can't be predicted as the adsorption is not homogeneous throughout the surface and SEM has analyzed in a very small area (200 µm × 200 µm). EDX result suggested that nails without arsenic consisted iron, oxygen around 37.59% and 62.41% respectively by mass (Fig. 1). And arsenic was not detected in that sample. Nails having with anoxic As(III) consists iron, oxygen, and arsenic around 45.26%, 53.13% and 1.61% by mass respectively (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Elemental information (W-SEM result) of rusting nail without arsenic.

Fig. 2. Elemental information (W-SEM result) of rusting nail having with anoxic As(III).

B.2. X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) result :

Same iron nails which were used to get maximum adsorption capacity were used for XPS study. Nails after separating the head from the nail; were run in XPS with Auger Electron Spectroscopy (AES) Module Mode/Supplier : PHI 5000 Versa Prob11, FEI Inc. The XPS was analyzed to find element phases on the surface of the nail. As(III), As(V) has 3d Binding Energy (BE) at 44.2 and 45.5 eV respectively (Wagner, Gale and Raymond, 1979). BE for Fe2p of chemical state like Fe metal, FeO, Fe₂O₃, Fe_{0.9}O are found at 706.7, 709.6, 710.8 and 723.2 respectively (Biesinger *et al.*, 2011; Uhlig *et al.*, 2001). From the XPS results which is shown in Fig. 3; it is clear that arsenic has adsorbed on iron oxides as well as onto metal iron.

Fig. 3. XPS result of anoxic rusting iron nails with As(III).

C. Batch study for rate of adsorption (k)

In Experiment-1; the batch study was done to get dynamics of the adsorption process (*k*) at different ages (like 1 day, 15 days, 30 days, 45 days etc.) of rusting nails. Results of Experiment-1 used to get a rate of adsorption for anoxic As(III) and anoxic As(V) which are shown in Figs. 4 and 5 respectively. The initial concentration of arsenic was taken 100 ppb (or 100 µg/L) and tested in 5 g rusted nails.

It was found that rate of removal for As(III) is more than As(V) by comparing two data up to 45 days which is shown in Figs. 6–9. Dixit and Hering, 2003 found sorption of As(III) onto iron oxides like hydrous ferric oxide (HFO), goethite (FeOOH) and magnetite (Fe₃O₄) is more favorable than As(V) at

Fig. 4. Rate of removal for anoxic As(III).

Fig. 5. Rate of removal for anoxic As(V).

pH above 7 which supports my result. And sorption of As(v) is better than As(III) below pH 6. Both As(III) and As(V) sorb strongly to iron oxide; however, adsorption behavior depends on the mineralogy of the iron oxides as well as competing ions like phosphate, silicic acid, and bicarbonates (R., B. and L., 2005; Appelo *et al.*, 2002). Phosphate; if the concentration in ground water is more than arsenic, is particularly effective at competing with As(v) for adsorption on iron oxides (A., E. and S., 1998). The presence of phosphate may be one of the possible

Fig. 6. Removal efficiency for anoxic As(III) and anoxic As(V) for (a) 1, (b) 15, (c) 30 and (d) 45 days rusted nails.

reason behind lower rate of removal for As(v) than As(III). It has been observed that more than 90% removal achieved in both As(III) and As(v) for the anoxic condition after 12 h when the initial arsenic concentration was 100 ppb.

D. Batch study for maximum adsorption capacity (q_{max}) of rusting iron nails

Experiment-2 was done to get the maximum capacity of rusted iron nails per g considering that all nails have taken equal part in sorption. The initial concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (500 ppb) was spiked in four different cases (anoxic As(III), anoxic As(V), oxic As(III) and oxic As(V)) having with 5 g of rusting nails. After 24 h final arsenic concentration was checked. This process was continued till breakthrough. Sequestration curves are shown in Fig. 7. Maximum adsorption capacity for anoxic As(III), anoxic As(V), oxic As(III) and oxic As(V) were found 528.32, 488, 531.87 and 516.25 μg per g of rusted nail.

E. Column study

Column test (Experiment-3) was designed to know practical applicability and performance of rusting nails. Results are shown in Table 2. The idea to use filter was to get maximum volume of filtered water with an arsenic concentration of below 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (WHO standard for drinking water) taking initial concentration 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$. Iron concentrations (Table 3) and turbidity (Table 2) of outlet samples were measured periodically in MAPES and Nephelometer respectively. Total 820 lit. arsenic was filtered in four phases to check the performance for As(III), As(v) and 1 : 1 total As and final concentration was below 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$. Total adsorbed arsenic was quite low compared to batch study. One possible reason may be that all nails did not take part in adsorption as arsenic passed through few certain paths. Tracer study also supported that claim as I found actual retention time is less than the theoretical retention time.

Fig. 7. Sequestration curve for (a) anoxic As(III), (b) anoxic As(V), (c) oxic As(III) and (d) oxic As(V).

Table 2. Performance of the filter

Performance of filter						
Type of arsenic	Vol of water passed before that (L)	Initial conc. (ppb)	Final conc. (ppb)	Flow rate (ml/min)	Turbidity (NTU)	
1st phase	As(III)	5	96.39 ± 2.61	6.06 ± 1.58	40	2.4
		50	92.887 ± 4.14	1.14 ± 0.64	32	2.42
		75	108.84 ± 2.16	2.78 ± 0.17	32	2.5
		100	101.56 ± 1.68	1.97 ± 0.12	32	3.4
2nd phase	As(V)	120	93.35 ± 1.42	4.01 ± 2.42	35	–
		140	118.32 ± 2.34	1.54 ± 1.24	32	–
		160	117.12 ± 3.16	7.98 ± 1.12	40	–
		220	108.34 ± 1.92	9.86 ± 0.61	38	–
		300	112.16 ± 4.16	10.29 ± 0.12	40	–
3rd phase	1 : 1 total As	320	93.09 ± 1.28	10.09 ± 0.38	38	–
		340	109.35 ± 2.84	8.44 ± 1.38	32	–
		360	100.6 ± 1.61	9.48 ± 1.47	32	–
		480	105.52 ± 2.18	7.27 ± 0.16	34	–
		500	97.06 ± 1.43	8.94 ± 0.14	36	–
4th phase	As(III)	740	92.67 ± 1.91	9.59 ± 1.35	40	6.38
		800	117.24 ± 1.38	6.12 ± 2.64	40	6.97
		820	90.93 ± 2.68	14.89 ± 1.48	40	7.32
		840	97.67 ± 1.89	21.83 ± 1.94	40	7.16
		860	96.28 ± 3.16	16.82 ± 3.16	38	6.17

Table 3. Iron concentration at outlet

Sl. No.	Fe conc. (ppb)	Vol. of water passed before (L)
1.	185.63	25
	117.74	
2.	153.28	300
	183.74	
3.	385.2	860
	371.62	
	387.46	

IV. Conclusion

Based on the study; it is clear that both As(III) and As(V) can be efficiently removed from water using rusting nails. The maximum adsorption capacity of rusted nail was found 531.87 μg per g of rusted nail for oxidic As(III) and least maximum adsorption capacity was found 488 μg per g of rusted nail for anoxic As(V). Maximum adsorption capacity for anoxic As(III), anoxic As(V), oxidic As(III) and oxidic As(V) were found 528.32, 488, 531.87 and 516.25 μg per g of rusted nail respectively. It is assumed that all nails have taken equal part in adsorption procedure.

The rate of removal for As(III) is more than As(V) which also supports various experiments^{12,13}. It is observed that at the first phase (approximately before 240 min) the removal efficiency is more. And in the second phase (approximately after 240 min) removal efficiency is less which leads to the possible existence of two or more reaction rate constant (k) of removal. Removal efficiency increased over time to reach a maximum around 90 days of rusted nails followed by decrease the rate of removal.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (WSEM) morphology images show different stages of iron oxides formation on the surface of nails. EDX shows the presence of arsenic on the surface.

X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) results show the formation of different iron oxides like FeOOH, FeO, Fe₂O₃, Fe_{0.9}O etc. onto rusting iron nails. Adsorption of arsenite and arsenate also visible onto the iron surface.

Total 820 lit. (380 lit. As(III), 240 lit. As(V) and 200 lit. of 1 : 1 total As) of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ arsenic con-

taminated water can be treated at a flow rate of 32–40 ml/min by using 1500 g of 6 mm rusting nails in a 7 cm diameter and 11.5 cm long column. This type of column can serve a household for around 3 months which has a drinking water demand 10 lit. per day. The cost of 1500 g fresh nails is Rs. 234. And considering lump sum cost (like acid wash, oven, sand, cotton and steel platform which were used to make the filter system) of Rs. 50; total cost to treat 820 lit. of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ arsenic is around Rs. 284. The cost to treat per lit. arsenic contaminated water having concentration 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ is around Rs. 0.35; which is very cheap.

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